

ANALYSIS OF FOREIGN EXPERIENCES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF IDEOLOGICAL COMPETENCE OF FUTURE PEDAGOGUES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13911994>

Abstract: The theoretical-methodological foundations of developing ideological competence of future pedagogues, the practical methodical system of developing ideological competence of future pedagogues and the effectiveness of developing ideological competence of future pedagogues are studied in the article. Also, The need and priorities for developing ideological competence of future pedagogues are analyzed.

Key words: ideological competence of pedagogues, competence, improvement, pedagogical, technological, model, didactic, spiritual-ethical competence, cognitive, assessment, conceptual basis.

INTRODUCTION. Today's information circulation is playing a role as a "weapon of popular culture–ideological warfare" in the conditions of accelerated globalization. Its difference from hot weapons of war is that in the form of "soft power" it is slowly entering societies where national culture is a priority, under the guise of culture, without political claims. The development of ideological and ideological competence in future pedagogues is an important part of the educational process and is of great importance in the professional activity of future teachers.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS. The analysis of ideological and ideological processes, the issues of ideological education and the formation of ideological immunity have been studied by several scientists and are still being studied today. In particular, the national idea and self-awareness are problematic B. Saparov, the concept of ideology, the importance of national ideology in raising a well-rounded personality, personal spirituality and problems of national education M. Kuronov, theoretical and historical-progressive issues of our national spirituality and ideology M. Bekmurodov, the essence of the national idea, which is the main source of social-national consciousness, activity, national pride and the feeling of pride, I. Ergashev, the inextricable connection and connection of the concepts of spirituality and ideology, issues of independence and formation of individual spirituality were expressed in the researches of A. Ochildiyev, problems of formation of spiritual and ideological potential in the process of national development by H. Jumaniyozov, problem of succession in national ideology O. Mamatov.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. The development of ideological and ideological competence in future pedagogues is an important task, because this competence plays a key role in ensuring the effectiveness of a pedagogue's professional activity. Advanced foreign experiences for the development of such competence can be analyzed below:

1. Sweden: The education system in Sweden is focused on creativity and independent thinking. Educators complete special programs to inform students about different cultures and worldviews and develop their thinking skills.

2. Finland: The Finnish education system focuses on regional and national identity. In order to develop ideological and ideological competence of pedagogues, in addition to teaching them national history, culture and values, trainings are conducted to strengthen intercultural relations.

3. Canada: In Canada, as part of pedagogical training, students are offered courses on understanding cultural differences and developing tolerance. This gives students the opportunity to respect and work effectively with people with different worldviews.

4. USA: Many US universities offer programs to educators that teach them about issues such as social justice, democracy, and human rights. At the same time, it is a priority to develop students' ability to think critically in order to form their own views.

5. Germany: Germany's educational system is built on the concept of national identity and social responsibility. Special seminars are held for students of pedagogic faculties, where ideological and ideological concepts are discussed.

Based on these foreign experiences, it becomes clear that there is a need to introduce programs covering topics such as independent thinking, cultural tolerance and social responsibility in the Uzbek education system. In addition, it is possible to conduct appropriate trainings for pedagogues and develop their ideological and ideological competence.

In developed countries, the national idea combines the goals of the state with the goals of the people, the formation of the belief of a single territory - a single people, combining the concepts of the Motherland and the state, the people and the nation from an ideological point of view, and mobilizes the people of the countries towards a common goal. we are happy

For example, the Japanese national idea was formed on the basis of the system of values "History - Shintoism - Confucianism - Samurai will". In Japan, the value system was used as a means of inculcating the national idea. As a result, the national idea, based on the trinity of "National idea - national

economy - national development", became the support of the "Japanese miracle", a source of spiritual strength. In Japan's "Fundamental Law on Education", educational institutions are entrusted with the mission of building a nation that adheres to the ideals of peace and humanity. That is, the full development of personal qualities; education of peace-loving state and society builders, truthfulness and justice; personal freedom; diligence; responsibility; independent thinking; cooperation with others, independent opinion; understand traditionalism and modernity; readiness for international cooperation; possession of daily life skills; mental and physical strength; the qualities of being happy and harmonizing with others are being formed.

In the document called "Qualities of an Ideal Japanese Boy and Girl" released for educational institutions, the task of forming 16 qualities in Japanese youth is defined. 16 virtues are divided into 4 groups. These are: 1) personal qualities: freedom, development of individuality, being independent, being able to control one's desires, having a sense of piety (respect); 2) qualities characteristic of the head of the family: the ability to turn one's home into a place of love, comfort and education; 3) social qualities: dedication to one's work, contribution to the well-being of society, creativity, respect for national (social) values; 4) citizenship qualities: it teaches loyalty to the motherland, appreciation of state symbols, social activity, and the best national qualities.

In the formation of the national idea and national consciousness in China, the national ground - Confucius's teaching is referred to. China used the legacy of Confucius not as a religious doctrine, but as a moral (for social skills) basis. In this country, the formation of a bigoted attitude towards the doctrine was prevented. Qualities such as "Goodness", "Truthfulness", "Politeness", "Wisdom", "Trustworthiness" were defined and practiced as the five main pillars of Confucian ethics. These qualities have gained a priority position in China's spiritual and ideological policy. This can be seen in the fact that spiritual education in China is organized on the basis of the idea of "serving and being loyal to the Motherland". In youth education, this principle teaches young people to maintain a balance between personal needs and collective needs.

Countries with a practical, pragmatic and integrative approach to the idea of a perfect person quickly extracted "benefits" from theoretical rules for today and tomorrow. Experimental pedagogy developed. They are turning the invisible theoretical concepts of education into visible things - images, behavioral technologies, forming the most necessary qualities in young people.

For example, in the US program "America - 2000: Education Development Strategy (1991)", priority was given to honesty, persistence in purpose, correctness (impartiality), thoroughness and personal responsibility as qualities characteristic of a mature person. Also, 60 basic virtues are being formed in young Americans, such as courage, selflessness, stability, determination, diligence, empathy, and tolerance.

Great Britain's National Commission for Education (1993) in the school: instill in young people truthfulness, respect for others, commitment to duty before society, caring for people, respect for cultural heritage, becoming citizens of a democratic free society, tolerance entrusted with the tasks of inculcating, raising morally and intellectually strong individuals.

According to the instructions of the French Ministry of Education, responsible, proud, respectful of others, ready to cooperate with others, against racism, accepting multiculturalism, combining his love for France with the ideas of Liberty, Equality, Fraternity It is intended to educate a person with the qualities of a person of a developed democratic society.

The US government oversees the upbringing of a specific set of qualities in its citizens from childhood. Pedagogical scientists believe that these character traits can be seen in the behavior of every American. For example, it is distinguished by "behaving freely and calmly in front of others, alienation from the "imperfection complex", being able to get out of any complex and tense situations with ease without getting confused, internal freedom is clearly manifested within the framework of political culture and legality. These mental characteristics are laid from childhood." In the educational systems of developed countries, active citizenship position, high morals, and spiritual values are preserved. Preservation and teaching of these values is defined as the central task of education policy. During the analysis of the higher education models of the developed countries, it is concluded that education is the formation of a set of qualities such as social, political, economic and cultural knowledge and awareness of one's rights, social activity by means of pedagogical influence on students. possible The first priority is to educate young people about their duty to society and the state.

CONCLUSION. Certain principles are followed in training the above qualities. Including developing a strategy of spiritual education, ensuring public participation in the educational process, the accuracy of the qualities being formed, the relationship of education with the content of education, education with the help of examples and experience, evaluating the results of educational

work, with educational work integration of principles such as training of working professors and continuous improvement of their qualifications, organization of student activities based on educational goals, programming of education and ensuring its effectiveness are followed.

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